

The Human Pressure Index (HPI): integrating cumulative anthropogenic pressures into SEEA-EA ecosystem condition accounts

Xavier Lecomte^{a,*}, Valentine Aubard^a, Graciela M. Rusch^b, Bálint Czúcz^b, Eszter Tanács^c, Isabel Nicholson Thomas^d, Chiara Cortinovis^e, Sara Vallecillo^f, Joana Seguin^g, Fernando Santos-Martín^h, Adrienne Grêt-Regamey^d, Philip Roche^{a,*}

^a Aix-Marseille Univ, INRAE, UMR RECOVER, 3275 Route de Cézanne, 13182 Aix-en-Provence cedex, 05, France

^b Norwegian Institute for Nature Research, P.O. Box 5685 Torgarden, NO-7485 Trondheim, Norway

^c HUN-REN Centre for Ecological Research, Institute of Ecology and Botany, H-2163 Vácrátót, Alkotmány utca 2-4., Hungary

^d Planning of Landscape and Urban Systems, Institute for Spatial and Landscape Development, ETH Zürich, Stefano-Franscini-Platz 5, 8093 Zürich, Switzerland

^e Department of Civil, Environmental and Mechanical Engineering, University of Trento, via Mesiano 77, 38123 Trento, Italy

^f Unisystems Luxembourg Sarl, 29 Rue Du Puits Romain, L-8070 Bertrange, Luxembourg (work carried out for the European Commission Joint Research Centre, Ispra, Italy)

^g Leibniz University Hannover, Institute of Earth System Sciences, Physical Geography and Landscape Ecology, Schneiderberg 50, 30167 Hannover, Germany

^h Rey Juan Carlos University of Madrid, Department of Environmental Technologies, Spain

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ABSTRACT

Effective ecosystem assessment and environmental planning require spatially explicit indices capturing how human-driven stressors affect ecosystems. Global assessments, including IPBES, identify land-use change, pollution, and invasive alien species (IAS) as major drivers of biodiversity loss. Yet these pressures remain insufficiently operationalised within ecosystem accounting frameworks such as SEEA-EA, limiting their direct policy application.

To bridge this gap, we propose a pressure-based conceptual framework aligned with the hierarchical structure of SEEA-EA ecosystem condition, which explicitly distinguishes anthropogenic pressures from ecosystem state variables and enables their systematic representation within ecosystem accounting. We operationalise this framework through the Human Pressure Index (HPI), a harmonised and spatially explicit composite index for European terrestrial ecosystems. HPI integrates 16 pressure indicators into three modular pressure-specific indices aligned with the IPBES drivers (land-use, pollution, and IAS), enabling both cumulative and driver-specific analyses.

HPI shows a strong negative association with the Biodiversity Intactness Index (BII), with pollution emerging as the strongest correlate of BII variation. A GAM–Beta model captures nonlinear biodiversity responses along the pressure gradient, explaining 40% of deviance and revealing saturation effects at high pressure levels. Comparisons with the Global Human Modification (GHM) index highlight complementarities between structural modification (GHM) and diffuse functional pressures (HPI).

Overall, this study provides a scalable and transferable pressure-based framework for the systematic integration of anthropogenic pressures within ecosystem condition assessment. HPI offers a policy-ready, spatially explicit tool for mapping cumulative pressures across ecosystems and supports environmental monitoring, policy evaluation and strategic planning across governance levels.

1. Introduction

Global assessments, notably by the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, highlight the

urgent need to reverse trends of biodiversity loss, land degradation and disruption of ecosystem services (IPBES, 2019). Although the importance of conserving and sustainably managing ecosystems has long been recognised (MEA (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment), 2005),

* Corresponding authors.

E-mail addresses: xavier.lecomte@inrae.fr (X. Lecomte), philip.roche@inrae.fr (P. Roche).

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maintaining ecosystems in a condition that supports biodiversity and ecosystem services remains a major challenge. In Europe, this challenge underpins ambitious policy commitments. The EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 (EC, 2020; EC, 2020) calls for large-scale restoration actions and an expansion of protected areas, while the Nature Restoration Regulation establishes legally binding restoration targets across EU Member States (EU, 2024).

The major direct drivers of biodiversity loss, i.e., land-use change, invasive alien species (IAS), overexploitation of species, pollution and climate change, were first formalised in the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MEA, 2005), refined by IPBES (IPBES, 2019), and embedded in international policy frameworks such as the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD, 2020) (Fig. 1). Translating these drivers into ecosystem degradation requires clarifying the human pressures through which they operate. Following Burkhard et al. (2018) and Czúcz et al. (2021a), human pressures are defined here as anthropogenic processes or activities that directly alter ecosystem structure, functioning and biodiversity through physical, chemical or biological stressors (Côté et al., 2016). Pressures thus encompass both human activities and the biophysical stressors they generate. This definition is consistent with major ecological assessment frameworks, including the EU MAES initiative (Maes et al., 2018, 2020), the Living Planet Index (WWF, 2018), the IPBES Global Assessment and the IUCN threats classification scheme (IUCN, 2020).

Human pressures have fundamentally altered species assemblages and ecosystem functioning, leading to biodiversity loss, ecosystem degradation, and disruption of ecosystem service provision, across terrestrial, freshwater, and marine systems (Keck et al., 2025). Agricultural intensification offers a clear example: between 1980 and 2016, increased pesticide and fertiliser use in Europe significantly reduced farmland bird populations (Rigal et al., 2023), particularly among invertebrate-feeding species critical for natural pest control service (Díaz-Sieffer et al., 2022). In extreme cases, pressures may induce loss of resilience, regime shifts or ecological collapse (Bergstrom et al., 2021; Rocha, 2022).

Capturing these pressures requires indicators that reflect both the human activities driving change and their biophysical manifestations. The DPSIR (Driver–Pressure–State–Impact–Response) framework (EEA

(European Environment Agency), 1999), explicitly distinguishes pressures from ecosystem state, which is foundational for diagnosing causes of change and designing effective policy responses (Müller and Burkhard, 2012). The European Commission's work on environmental pressure indicators (EC (European Commission), 1999), as well as the MAES assessments, operationalises this distinction by using both pressure and state indicators in ecosystem evaluations (Maes et al., 2018, 2020).

Despite its extensive application (e.g., Maxim and Spangenberg, 2009; Kuldna et al., 2009; Santos-Martín et al., 2013), DPSIR has gradually been superseded in environmental reporting by the System of Environmental-Economic Accounting (SEEA). Within the SEEA Central Framework (CF), flow-based stressors such as air emissions and wastewater discharges are recorded as residual flows from the economy to the environment (UN, 2014). The SEEA Ecosystem Accounting (EA) framework, in contrast, focuses on ecosystem extent, condition and services (UN, 2024), and does not include a dedicated pressure account. As a result, pressure-type variables occasionally appear in condition accounts as proxies when suitable state indicators are lacking, thereby blurring the causal distinctions central to DPSIR. A recent review shows that a substantial share of indicators used in ecosystem condition assessments represent pressures or auxiliary variables rather than ecosystem state characteristics (e.g., land-use intensity or fertiliser and pesticide application) (Nicholson Thomas et al., 2025). This lack of explicit conceptual and accounting articulation helps explain why, as underscored in the proposed update of SEEA-CF (Obst and Bogaart, 2025), linkages between flow-based pressures in CF and ecosystem-condition reporting in SEEA-EA remain not yet operationalised, leaving the representation of pressures implicit and fragmented. Clarifying how pressures are represented is therefore essential for linking SEEA-based reporting to policy obligations.

Existing indices, such as the Human Footprint Index (Venter et al., 2016) and the Global Human Modification Index (GHM) (Theobald et al., 2025), provide useful baselines for quantifying human modification, but they primarily represent structural pressures associated with land conversion, infrastructure and accessibility. Only GHM incorporates a limited subset of pollution-related variables (i.e., solid waste and low-intensity air pollution), and neither index captures key

Fig. 1. A) Main pressures on habitats and species and representation at European level (adapted from EEA Report No 10/2020 (EEA, 2020)) and B) Example of declines in nature at global scale, emphasizing declines in biodiversity (IPBES (Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services), 2019).

functional stressors such as nutrient surpluses, pesticide inputs, soil contamination or IAS.

This study addresses these gaps by establishing a clear conceptual separation between pressures and ecosystem state, consistent with SEEA-EA principles, and by operationalising three major IPBES drivers through harmonised, spatially explicit European indices, thereby providing a concrete foundation for future pressure accounting at global scale.

To operationalise this approach, we developed a typology of human pressure indicators structured to mirror the SEEA-EA condition typology, thereby ensuring conceptual alignment while maintaining a clear distinction between pressures and ecosystem state. Building on this typology, we constructed the Human Pressure Index (HPI), an aggregated characterisation of anthropogenic pressures on European terrestrial ecosystems. Indicators were then grouped using direct drivers of biodiversity loss identified by IPBES, providing an ecologically grounded and internationally recognised classification. HPI integrates three domains: land-use, pollution and IAS pressures. Land-use pressure here refers exclusively to pressures arising from ongoing land-use practices (e.g., soil sealing, fragmentation, management intensity), excluding land-cover transformations, which are captured in the SEEA-EA framework by ecosystem extent accounts. Other IPBES drivers were not included in HPI due to current limitations in spatially explicit datasets and methodological challenges associated with their integration into a continental-scale pressure index. Species exploitation lacks spatially explicit European datasets suitable for integration, while climate change was excluded for methodological reasons. Current climate datasets do not yet capture the region-specific climatic pressures relevant for ecosystems, and climate change operates primarily through large-scale climatic processes and indirect ecological responses that cannot be robustly spatially attributed at the spatial resolution required for the HPI. Although climate change is a major direct driver, its highly heterogeneous and process-specific impacts require more refined spatial indicators before it can be meaningfully incorporated.

By integrating these three domains, HPI provides a comprehensive measure of human pressures while enabling separate analyses of each thematic sub-index. To evaluate the ecological relevance of HPI, we examined its relationship with the Biodiversity Intactness Index (BII) and compared its spatial patterns with those of the Global Human Modification (GHM) index. Anchoring HPI in a SEEA-compatible indicator typology, while using the IPBES driver framework to define ecologically meaningful pressure domains, establishes a coherent conceptual framework for integrating human pressures into ecosystem condition assessment. The HPI framework is designed to be scalable and transferable, addressing the need for harmonised pressure indices capable of supporting ecosystem accounting and tracking progress toward international commitments, including the Convention on Biological Diversity's 2030 targets (CBD, 2020) and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, particularly the SDG 15 (Life on Land) (UN DESA, 2025).

2. Methods

2.1. Advancing ecosystem accounting: A proposal for SEEA-EA-consistent typology of pressure indicators

We developed a comprehensive and innovative typology of pressure indicators. To ensure conceptual coherence and compatibility with the SEEA-EA ecosystem condition typology, we adopted the same hierarchical structure: abiotic, biotic and landscape groups (Czúcz et al., 2021b) (Table 1). This alignment allows pressures to be organised using the same biophysical logic as condition variables, facilitating explicit links between human activities and resulting changes in ecosystem state. It enhances comparability and interoperability with ecosystem assessments, enabling pressure information to fit in a harmonised way into accounting and reporting workflows. The typology applies across

Table 1

Pressure indicator typology: Groups, classes, indicator categories and sub-categories used for the identification of the pressure metrics for ecosystems, according to the SEEA-EA framework.

Group	Class	Category	Sub-category
A - Abiotic Pressure	AP1 - Physical	Water	Water abstraction
		Soil	Imperviousness
		Air	Erosion
	AP2 - Chemical	Water	Pollutants
		Soil / Sediments	Pollutants
B - Biotic Pressure	BP1 - Compositional	Species	Pathogens and diseases
			Invasive Alien Species
C - Landscape Pressure	LP1 - Physical	Land-use	Intensity
	LP2 - Structural	Fragmentation	Mesh density

terrestrial, freshwater and marine ecosystems, with sufficient flexibility to incorporate ecosystem-specific sub-categories where needed.

To ensure comprehensive coverage of categories and sub-categories, we reviewed classification and indicator sets from the EU MAES initiative (Maes et al., 2018, 2020) and the SEEA-EA-aligned framework of Vallecillo et al. (2022), which informed the conceptual structure of our typology.

For each sub-category, the appropriate metrics should be selected according to the following criteria (sensu, Czúcz et al., 2021a):

- 1. Ecological relevance:** Indicators must represent human pressures that cause biotic, abiotic and/or landscape degradation in ecosystem condition.
- 2. Validity and reliability:** Indicators must accurately represent the characteristics of the sub-category and be based on reproducible, methodologically robust data sources.
- 3. Data availability and cross-ecosystem compatibility:** Indicators must be based on datasets available at required scale, consistently defined across regions/countries, and applicable across different ecosystem types.
- 4. Spatial explicitness:** Indicators must be spatially explicit, capturing spatial variability and enabling integration within spatially resolved assessments.

In this typology, abiotic physical pressures refer to direct alterations of environmental components (e.g., soil imperviousness), whereas landscape physical pressures represent pressures arising from the intensity and spatial organisation of land-use practices.

2.2. Construction of the Human Pressure Index (HPI)

HPI encompassed 27 European Union Member States, focusing on terrestrial ecosystems, as defined by the Corine Land Cover (CLC) classification system. Croatia and Cyprus were excluded because the required datasets were not consistently available; however, their combined territory represents less than 2% of the EU-27 land area and does not affect the representativeness of the index at the European scale. Although outside the EU-27, Norway and Switzerland were explored for potential inclusion, but their statistics are not fully harmonised with EU standards.

Although SEEA-EA provides a clear framework for organising ecosystem condition indicators, it does not prescribe how they should be aggregated. Instead, it emphasises that any aggregation must be based on thematically meaningful groupings, supported by ecological rationale and the purpose of the assessment. SEEA-EA explicitly supports the construction of thematic sub-indices as an intermediate step prior to the production of aggregated indices (UN, 2024). We thus structured HPI into three pressure-specific indices: land-use, pollution and IAS, drawing

on IPBES to define ecologically consistent and policy-relevant pressure domains. The overall workflow consisted of four steps:

1. **Selection and classification of variables:** Pressure variables were selected based on the pressure indicator typology and organised into pressure specific domains.
2. **Scaling:** We produced ‘pressure indicators’ by standardizing pressure variables, ensuring comparability across different measurement scales and units.
3. **Weighting:** We assigned a relative importance to different pressure indicators based on their documented ecological impacts.
4. **Aggregation:** We aggregated the weighted indicators into comprehensive sub-indices and into HPI.

2.2.1. Selection and classification of the variables

According to our typology, we selected available spatially explicit variables that represent each sub-category (Table 2).

Abiotic physical pressures included the Water Exploitation Index Plus (WEI+), soil imperviousness, and soil erosion. WEI+ indicates water stress, while soil imperviousness and erosion capture impacts on infiltration, runoff and hydrological functioning. Soil erosion was assessed separately for cropland (tillage and harvesting) and forest (harvesting and fire disturbance). Natural areas were assumed to experience negligible direct human-induced erosion at the continental scale, although local grazing or recreational pressures effects may occur and could lead to localized underestimation.

Abiotic chemical pressures included AOT40 (ozone exceedance), nitrogen deposition, fertilizer surpluses, pesticide pollution and exceedances of critical loads for heavy metals. AOT40 and nitrogen deposition affect vegetation and soil functioning across ecosystems, while fertilizer surpluses, heavy metals and pesticides, although exerting broader impacts, were restricted to agroecosystems, reflecting their predominant origin. Pesticide pollution was represented by a pesticide risk score integrating application intensity and ecotoxicological thresholds (Tang et al., 2021).

Biotic compositional pressures were captured through the cumulative potential pressure from 66 IAS of EU concern, aggregated across major terrestrial ecosystem types (Polce et al., 2023).

Physical landscape pressures included forest management intensity (Scherpenhuijzen et al., 2025), which classifies forests into five

management regimes based on disturbance history, age structure, and species composition, and agricultural management intensity (Rega et al., 2020), an energy-based indicator of external inputs per hectare.

Structural landscape pressure included fragmentation, reflecting the degree to which infrastructure and urbanisation break continuous habitats into smaller patches.

Pathogens and diseases were not included because harmonised, EU-wide, spatially explicit (“wall-to-wall”) datasets suitable for consistent continental-scale integration are currently lacking. Existing information is typically fragmented or case-specific and reported at heterogeneous spatial and temporal resolutions. In addition, pathogen dynamics reflect both anthropogenic influences and natural ecological or climatic variability, and currently available data do not allow robust attribution specifically to human-driven pressures at EU scale. Water-related pollution was also excluded because EU-wide freshwater datasets primarily describe waterbody quality rather than pollutant concentrations, which are monitored at point locations that cannot be reliably spatialised. Moreover, water pollution largely originates from terrestrial activities and is more appropriately assessed using dedicated pressure indices rather than integrated into a terrestrial pressure framework. The operational selection of indicators within this framework depends on the availability of suitable harmonised datasets at European scale. The HPI framework was therefore designed with a modular structure, allowing additional pressure indicators to be integrated as new datasets become available without altering the underlying conceptual typology. Full details and bibliographic references are provided in the Supplementary Materials SM1.

These indicators were then classified within the IPBES domains used for the aggregation process (Table 2). Variables reflecting physical or structural modification (i.e., imperviousness, soil erosion, water abstraction, management intensities, fragmentation) were assigned to Land-use pressure. Variables representing chemical inputs, atmospheric deposition or toxicity exceedances (i.e., ozone, nitrogen deposition, fertilizer surplus, pesticides, heavy metals), were assigned to Pollution pressure. IAS were treated separately following the IPBES classification.

2.2.2. Data alignment and resampling

To ensure spatial consistency and comparability across indicators and regions, all spatial datasets were aligned and resampled using Google Earth Engine (GEE) (Gorelick et al., 2017). Data were reprojected to the European ETRS89-extended coordinate reference system

Table 2

List of available spatially explicit variables selected to assess pressure in terrestrial ecosystems in Europe (EEA: European Environment Agency; JRC: Joint Research Center; ESDAC: European Soil Data Centre; EASIN: European Alien Species Information Network). Variables were classified according to the SEEA-EA pressure typology and to the IPBES categories.

Group	Class	Indicator Category	Variable	IPBES category	Unit	Source	Resolution	Reference year
Abiotic pressure	Physical	Water	Water Exploitation Index (WEI+)	Land-use	% of renewable water resources	EEA	Sub-river basins	2019
		Soil	Soil imperviousness	Land-use	%	Copernicus	10 m	2018
		Soil erosion cropland	Land-use	Mg/ha/yr	JRC / ESDAC	100 m	2010	
	Chemical	Air	Soil erosion forest	Land-use	Mg/ha/yr	JRC / ESDAC	100 m	2010
			AOT40 Ozone vegetation and crops	Pollution	($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$).h	EEA	2000 m	2018
		Nitrogen deposition	Pollution	mol.N.eq./ha/year	EEA	1°	2021	
		Soil	Fertilizer surplus (N, P)	Pollution	kg/ha/yr	EEA	1000 m	2010
Pesticide risk score	Pollution	Unitless	Tang et al. (2021)	10,000 m	2015			
Exceedance of heavy metals input to the soil (Zn, Cu, Pb)	Pollution	mg/kg	EEA	1000 m	2010			
Biotic pressure	Compositional	Species	Pressure by invasive alien species	IAS	Unitless	Polce et al. (2023)	10,000 m	2019
Landscape pressure	Physical	Land-use	Forest management intensity	Land-use	Unitless	Scherpenhuijzen et al. (2025)	1000 m	1985–2023
			Agricultural management intensity	Land-use	MJ/ha	Rega et al. (2020)	1000 m	2007–2010
	Structural	Fragmentation	Effective Mesh Density	Land-use	Meshes/1000 km ²	EEA	100 m	2018

and mapped onto 1 km² reference grid. Resampling was performed using the default nearest-neighbour method, whereby each pixel of the target grid was assigned the value of the spatially closest source pixel based on Euclidean distance to the pixel centre. This approach preserves original data values and avoids smoothing effects associated with bilinear or bicubic interpolation (Lillesand et al., 2015). Vector datasets were rasterized using the *ee.FeatureCollection.reduceToImage* function with the *ee.Reducer.first()* reducer, resulting in a nearest-neighbour assignment of feature values to raster cells. As the source polygons did not spatially overlap, this direct vector-to-raster conversion was unambiguous. Nitrogen deposition point data were initially rasterized on their native grid (EPSG: 4326; 0.1° resolution) before being reprojected and resampled.

2.2.3. Variable diagnostics

An exploratory analysis was conducted to document the statistical properties and interrelationships among variables, included in the land-use and pollution pressure indices. This step was performed to ensure transparency in indicator preparation and did not serve for variable selection or inferential analysis. Despite the presence of moderate to strong correlations among some variables, all variables were retained for the index construction. This decision reflects the purpose of HPI, to capture the cumulative co-occurrence of human pressures rather than to isolate or interpret the effects of individual variables. In the context of composite pressure indices, correlated variables are therefore considered an expected and informative feature of pressure accumulation rather than a source of statistical redundancy (OECD, 2008). Detailed methods, and correlation results are provided in SM2.

2.2.4. Scaling of input variables

To ensure comparability across variables and enable aggregation, all input variables were normalised to a unitless scale ranging from 0 (no pressure) to 1 (highest pressure). For each variable, the minimum value observed within the study area was used as the lower anchor, representing negligible or absent human pressure. For most variables, this value was zero; for heavy metal exceedances, negative values were truncated to zero. For IAS, areas with no reported records in EU Member States were assigned a zero value, reflecting the absence of reported occurrences rather than confirmed absence. To limit the influence of extreme values in continuous variables, the upper anchor was defined as the 95th percentile of the observed distribution (OECD, 2008). This threshold caps values to prevent extreme outliers from disproportionately influencing the scaling of the index while preserving the relative ranking and identification of high-pressure areas. This approach improves the robustness of the index to outliers while maintaining its policy relevance at the continental scale. Ordinal variables were rescaled using their maximum class value. Indicator maps as shown in Figs. SM3.1 and SM3.2.

2.2.5. Input variables weighting

To account for varying degrees of impact that different stressors may have on ecosystems, we developed a weighting system (Table 3), determined through a combination of expert elicitation and statistical analysis. Building on IPBES, we first adopted the relative weights assigned to each driver, applying a normalization to ensure their combined weight reached 100%. This preserved their proportional influence and enabled meaningful comparisons across drivers. Each co-author ($n = 12$) then independently assigned relative scores to the indicators within their sub-index category, based on their perceived significance or impact. The expert panel consisted of researchers and practitioners involved in the study, representing institutions from several European countries and covering complementary expertise in ecosystem assessment (e.g., wetlands, forests, urban systems, agroecosystems, grasslands) and environmental pressures, ensuring that the weighting process reflected a broad range of ecosystem perspectives.

Table 3

Weighting scheme used to construct the pressure-specific indices and the Human Pressure Index. Indicator weights reflect expert-elicited assessments, while sub-index weights represent the relative contribution of IPBES direct drivers.

pressure-specific indices	Indicator	Indicator weight	Sub-index weight
Land-use	WEI+	0,139	0,55
	Imperviousness	0,155	
	Soil erosion cropland	0,147	
	Soil erosion forest	0,117	
	Forest management	0,141	
	Agricultural management	0,157	
	Fragmentation	0,144	
Pollution	AOT Ozone	0,111	0,23
	Nitrogen deposition	0,126	
	Soil N surplus	0,139	
	Soil P surplus	0,140	
	Pesticide risk score	0,165	
	Soil Cu exceedance	0,110	
	Soil Pb exceedance	0,111	
Soil Zn exceedance	0,098		
Invasive Alien Species	IAS pressure	1000	0,22

2.2.6. Aggregation

The final step involved a two-stage aggregation process. First, we constructed pressure-specific indices by aggregating the weighted, normalized metrics for each driver. For land-use and pollution, composite pressure maps were generated by applying a weighted additive approach, to produce a single pressure map per driver. This process follows principles used in cumulative impact assessment framework, which provide a structured approach for combining co-occurring pressures into a single measure (Jones, 2016). In contrast, IAS driver was represented by a pre-existing map, requiring no internal aggregation.

Subsequently, these pressure-specific indices were normalized to a 0–1 scale and aggregated using IPBES-assigned weights, via the same weighted arithmetic sum. This ensures that each stressor contributes proportionally to its estimated impact on biodiversity and ecosystem functioning, yielding the final HPI map.

2.2.7. Sensitivity analysis

We used a global Monte Carlo sensitivity analysis (Saltelli et al., 2008) to assess the robustness of the land-use and pollution sub-indices to uncertainty in expert-defined weights. To explore a broad uncertainty space, indicator weights were simultaneously perturbed ($\pm 50\%$, $\pm 100\%$) around their baseline values, while maintaining a total weight of one. The coefficient of variation was used as a global sensitivity metric, with low values indicating high robustness. To complement this global approach, we conducted a univariate (One-at-a-time, OAT) sensitivity analysis, perturbing each weight independently by $\pm 50\%$ and $\pm 100\%$ while renormalizing the set. This combined analysis allows to evaluate both overall and local sensitivities of the index to deviations in weighting choices (see SM4 for details).

2.3. Correlating human pressures with biodiversity integrity

We assessed the relationship between human pressures and biodiversity by analysing our HPI, its three pressure-specific indices, and the Biodiversity Intactness Index (BII). The BII, representing native species abundance relative to a reference state (Scholes and Biggs, 2005), was derived from the 2020 high-resolution (100 m) dataset (Gassert et al., 2022) available in the GEE Community Catalogue. Unlike our HPI, this BII dataset relies solely on land-cover classification and accessibility proxies, excluding key pressures like management intensity or pollution.

Normality tests indicated strong deviations from normality for all layers ($P < 0.001$), justifying the use of non-parametric approaches. To account for spatial autocorrelation, we assessed global spatial dependence using Monte Carlo permutation tests of Moran's I across multiple neighbourhood scales ($k = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10$), where k represents the number of nearest neighbouring cells. Multiple testing was corrected using Benjamini–Hochberg procedure. Significant spatial autocorrelation was detected across all scales ($P < 0.001$). Given consistent autocorrelation across neighbourhood sizes, we selected $k = 8$ as the optimal neighbourhood size, corresponding to a spatial extent of approximately 10–15 km, consistent with landscape-scale ecological processes at 1 km² resolution (Turner, 2005). Correlation analyses were therefore conducted using a spatially constrained permutation procedure designed to mitigate inflated significance arising from spatial autocorrelation.

To further assess the combined and relative effects of pressure-specific indices, we applied a Random Forest regression, a flexible machine-learning approach that accommodates non-linear relationships and multicollinearity (Breiman, 2001). Model performance was evaluated using the coefficient of determination (R^2) and the root mean squared error (RMSE), and variable importance metrics were used to quantify the relative contribution of individual pressure components.

Finally, to examine potential saturation of biodiversity responses under increasing pressure, we modelled the relationship between HPI and BII, using stratified samples extracted from full-resolution maps. Comparisons of alternative monotonic decreasing models indicated a nonlinear decline with pronounced heteroskedasticity. We therefore fitted a flexible Beta-family generalized additive model (GAM) to capture nonlinear responses while accounting for bounded response values and non-constant variance. Model performance was compared with the best-fitting exponential model using ΔAIC and adjusted R^2 , confirming the superior fit of the GAM framework.

Two reference points were derived from the GAM: HPI₅₀ at which BII is reduced by 50%, and a saturation threshold (HPI_{sat}), marking the transition from rapid biodiversity loss to a slower, saturating phase. HPI_{sat} was identified using a derivative-based criterion applied to the GAM-predicted curve, inspired by half-saturation concepts in ecological dose–response modelling but focusing on the rate of biodiversity decline rather than on response magnitude (Newman, 2019). This derivative-based approach provides an operational, model-based marker of saturation onset by capturing changes in the rate of biodiversity loss, a key but often overlooked dimension of ecosystem resilience (Cumming, 2011). By complementing magnitude-based thresholds, HPI_{sat} offers a relatively novel way to characterise nonlinear saturation dynamics along human-pressure gradients (Isbell et al., 2017). Robustness was assessed using alternative derivative thresholds (40% and 60%), yielding consistent estimates.

Full methodological details for all analyses are provided in SM5.

2.4. Comparing HPI to the Global Human Modification index

To compare HPI with measures of human modification, we used the 2020 Global Human Modification index (GHM; Theobald et al., 2025). GHM provides a high-resolution measure of cumulative structural pressures on terrestrial ecosystems across eight IUCN-aligned threat categories, primarily reflecting land conversion, built-up areas, resource extraction and transport infrastructure. We assessed the association between HPI and GHM using spatially constrained correlation analyses consistent with those described in Section 2.3. To examine differences between the two indices, we analysed HPI–GHM contrasts across major terrestrial ecosystem types derived from CLC map, excluding wetlands and water bodies. For each ecosystem type, we calculated the mean and standard deviation of HPI–GHM differences and the proportion of pixels where HPI exceeded or was lower than GHM. Details for all analyses are provided in SM5.

3. Results

3.1. Spatial patterns and drivers of human pressure on European terrestrial ecosystems

3.1.1. Human pressure index

HPI reveals pronounced continental-scale gradients of pressures across Europe (Fig. 2). Low HPI values dominate Northern Scandinavia (mean \pm SD: 0.13 ± 0.10) (Fig. 2A) and major mountain ranges, reflecting low land-use intensity, extensive forest cover and limited infrastructure development, although localised hotspots related to intensive forest management are apparent. In contrast, high-pressure levels occur across parts of Central and Western Europe, particularly in the Benelux region (0.55 ± 0.16) (Fig. 2B), across Germany, Western Poland and Northern Italy. These patterns reflect combined influence of intensive agriculture, legacy pollution, dense urban–industrial networks and highly developed transport corridors. Moderate to high HPI values characterise many Atlantic and Mediterranean coastal regions (0.41 ± 0.13) (Fig. 2C), where tourism, port activities and coastal urbanisation intensify cumulative pressures. Comparable pressure levels are also observed across parts of North-eastern Europe, driven primarily by intensive agriculture, widespread land-use modification and transport infrastructure. These areas exhibit marked spatial heterogeneity, with strong contrasts between intensively managed landscapes and less impacted surrounding areas.

Overall, HPI captures a complex spatial mosaic of cumulative pressures across Europe, highlighting both broad regional contrasts and finer-scale heterogeneity driven by the co-occurrence of multiple pressure domains.

3.1.2. Pressure-specific indices

The pressure-specific drivers show distinct yet partially overlapping spatial patterns (Figs. 3–5). Lower values of land-use pressure dominate Northern and mountainous regions (mean \pm SD: 0.19 ± 0.15) (Fig. 3A). In contrast, land-use pressure is widespread across large parts of Western and Central Europe (0.39 ± 0.13) (Fig. 3B), reflecting urbanisation, agricultural intensification and infrastructure development. Comparable pressure levels are also observed in Mediterranean coastal regions (0.41 ± 0.11) (Fig. 3C), where land-use pressure exhibits more fragmented and spatially heterogeneous pattern. Low pollution levels dominate Northern Europe and major mountain ranges (0.02 ± 0.02) (Fig. 4A), while higher pollution pressure occurs in intensively farmed and industrialised regions, with pronounced hotspots in the Benelux (0.39 ± 0.26) (Fig. 4B), Northern Italy, Western France and major urban areas. The Mediterranean inset (Fig. 4C) highlights sharp coastal–inland contrasts in pollution pressure (0.38 ± 0.22). IAS pressure displays a more spatially concentrated pattern, with low values across northern Europe (0.03 ± 0.10) (Fig. 5A) and mountain regions and high values in highly connected regions of Western and Central Europe (0.78 ± 0.32) (Fig. 5B), particularly around major ports, transport corridors and metropolitan areas. Intermediate levels are observed in parts of Southern Europe (0.21 ± 0.24) (Fig. 5C).

Overall, the three drivers capture complementary dimensions of human pressure, whose combined spatial patterns are consistent with the continental-scale gradients observed in the HPI map. High values concentrate in intensively managed and highly connected regions, while lower levels prevail across Northern and mountainous parts of Europe.

3.2. Sensitivity analysis

Coefficients of variation (CV) of mean index values across simulations with simultaneous random perturbation of weights were low. For the pollution index, CV values were $0.04 (\pm 50 \%)$ and $0.10 (\pm 100 \%)$, while the land-use index showed values of $0.08 (\pm 50 \%)$ and $0.17 (\pm 100 \%)$ (Table SM4.1). OAT sensitivity analysis showed a consistent linear response of both indices to changes in individual weights, with \pm

Fig. 2. Spatial distribution of the Human Pressure Index across Europe, expressed as normalized scores ranging from low (blue) to high (red) cumulative anthropogenic pressure. Insets highlight contrasting regional contexts: (A) low pressure levels in northern Scandinavia, (B) very high pressures in the Benelux region, and (C) moderate to high pressures in Mediterranean coastal regions. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

50 % perturbations producing approximately half the effect of ± 100 % changes, confirming proportionality and additivity. The composite indices exhibited low overall sensitivity to weight variations, with a maximum average change of 3.55 %. Sensitivity was highest for indicators with the largest initial weights: pesticides, phosphorus surplus and nitrogen deposition within pollution, and agricultural and forest management intensities within land-use (Table SM4.2). Soil imperviousness showed unexpectedly low sensitivity despite its relatively high weight, likely due to its localised distribution in urban and industrial areas and strong overlap with fragmentation patterns, limiting its marginal contribution (high correlation; Fig. SM2.2).

These analyses confirm that spatial patterns and relative pressure gradients remain stable under moderate to large weight perturbations, supporting the robustness of the weighting scheme.

3.3. Relationship with the Biodiversity Intactness Index

HPI correlated significantly and negatively with BII ($\rho = -0.59$, $P < 0.001$). Pollution showed significant association ($\rho = -0.72$, $P < 0.001$), while IAS ($\rho = -0.36$, $P = 0.09$) and land-use ($\rho = -0.32$, $P = 0.22$) showed weaker relationships with BII.

Random Forest regression showed strong predictive performance ($R^2 = 0.60$; RMSE = 0.11). Variable importance ranked pollution as the dominant predictor, followed by land-use and IAS (Table SM5.4).

The Beta-family GAM revealed a strong significant nonlinear relationship (edf = 4.98, $F = 443.47$, $P < 0.0001$, Table SM5.6), explaining

40% of deviance (adjusted $R^2 = 0.36$). BII declined monotonically with increasing HPI, with the rate of biodiversity loss slowing under higher pressure, approaching a lower asymptote around $BII \approx 0.38$ (Fig. 6). The GAM substantially outperformed the exponential model ($\Delta AIC = 591.55$; adjusted R^2 increase from 0.29 to 0.36).

Two reference points were derived from the GAM: $HPI_{50} = 0.66$, at which BII is reduced by 50% ($BII \approx 0.44$), and a saturation threshold at $HPI_{sat} \approx 0.57$, marking the transition to a slower, saturating phase of biodiversity loss. Alternative derivative thresholds (40% and 60%) yielded similar values (0.61 and 0.53), confirming the robustness of HPI_{sat} .

3.4. Comparison between HPI and GHM

HPI was significantly and positively correlated with GHM ($\rho = 0.59$, $P < 0.001$), indicating that both indices capture broadly similar spatial patterns of anthropogenic impact. However, analyses stratified by ecosystem type revealed systematic differences in the magnitude of pressures represented by the two metrics.

On average, HPI was lower than GHM in highly modified landscapes, especially in artificial surfaces (mean difference \pm SD = -0.36 ± 0.15 ; in 98 % of pixels) and agricultural areas (-0.11 ± 0.15 ; 78 %). Conversely, HPI tended to exceed GHM in more natural or semi-natural ecosystems, including forests ($+0.06 \pm 0.13$; 72 %), shrublands and heathlands ($+0.04 \pm 0.13$; 68 %), and natural grasslands ($+0.01 \pm 0.13$; 56 %). The strongest divergence occurred in mineral with sparsely

Fig. 3. Spatial distribution of land-use pressure across Europe. Land-use pressure reflects the intensity of urbanisation, agricultural land-use and infrastructure development. Insets highlight (A) low land-use pressure in northern and mountainous regions, (B) widespread land-use pressure across Western and Central Europe, and (C) comparable pressure levels in Mediterranean coastal regions, characterised by a more fragmented and spatially heterogeneous pattern.

vegetated areas ($+0.25 \pm 0.11$; 75 %), where HPI values were markedly higher than GHM (Fig. SM5.1). The spatial distribution of HPI–GHM differences across Europe is shown in the Supplementary Materials (Fig. SM5.2).

4. Discussion

4.1. Ecological interpretation of HPI

Although BII is a modelled biodiversity indicator derived from observed species responses to human pressures, correlating HPI with BII remains ecologically meaningful, given the limited overlap between the pressure indicators used in HPI and the spatial pressure proxies included in the BII modelling framework. In addition, because BII is derived from statistical relationships with a specific set of spatial human-pressure proxies, its sensitivity may vary across the different HPI pressure domains. HPI captures biodiversity decline gradients effectively, with its pollution sub-index showing strong and significant negative associations with BII, underscoring the central role of pollution-related pressures in biodiversity degradation (e.g., Pelosi et al., 2021; Galasso et al., 2025). The weaker relationship observed for land use likely reflects partial circularity between HPI imperviousness and the Built-Area component of BII (Gassert et al., 2022), as well as complex and potentially compensatory interactions among land-use pressures (e.g., Tschamtko et al., 2005) which may reduce the sensitivity of aggregated indicators to biodiversity responses at continental scale. For IAS, spatial scale mismatches with typically localized invasion impacts, combined with

regional reporting inconsistencies, likely contribute to the weaker association with BII and highlight potential mismatches in indicator sensitivity and spatial data resolution (Bacher et al., 2023).

The GAM captures rapid biodiversity loss at intermediate pressure levels followed by a saturating decline at high pressure (Guerrero et al., 2014; Liu et al., 2025), providing benchmarks along the pressure gradient (e.g., BII_{50} , HPI_{sat}) that reflect model-derived patterns rather than ecological tipping points. The convergence of correlation, Random Forest and GAM results indicates that HPI consistently captures broad gradients of human pressure associated with declining biodiversity intactness. These results should therefore be interpreted as evidence of macro-ecological consistency between gradient of human pressure and biodiversity responses, rather than as evidence of direct causal relationship. Further validation against independent biodiversity observations will strengthen its ecological credibility.

4.2. Comparison with GHM

HPI and GHM both capture broad gradients of human modification across Europe, but differ systematically across land-cover types, highlighting their complementarity. As a primarily structural index, GHM is most sensitive to highly modified environments such as urban areas. In contrast, HPI integrates functional pressures such as pollution, erosion, water exploitation and IAS. The novelty of the HPI lies in its integration of functional pressures alongside structural land-use pressures, enabling it to capture ecologically relevant degradation in natural and semi-natural ecosystems where land conversion remains limited. Higher

Fig. 4. Spatial distribution of pollution pressure across Europe. The map integrates multiple pollution-related indicators reflecting nutrient and chemical inputs from agriculture as well as urban and industrial emissions. Insets illustrate contrasting contexts: (A) low pollution levels in northern Europe and mountain regions, (B) high pollution pressure in intensively farmed and industrialised areas of Central Europe, and (C) intermediate levels in Mediterranean regions.

GHM values in agricultural areas reflect a conceptual divergence: GHM treats croplands as uniformly highly modified, whereas HPI emphasizes management- and pollution-related pressures that vary widely across farming systems and may remain moderate under extensive practices. Overall, the two indices are not redundant but complementary: GHM mainly reflects land conversion, consistent with ecosystem extent accounting under the SEEA framework, while HPI captures cumulative diffuse and management-related pressures influencing ecosystem integrity, supporting biodiversity monitoring and policy evaluation.

4.3. Strengths and strategic applications of the Human Pressure Index

4.3.1. Conceptual foundation in SEEA

HPI builds on the SEEA-EA framework, distinguishing ecosystem extent and condition accounts, and leverages SEEA-CF to contextualise pressures influencing ecosystems. Beyond the index itself, this study advances a pressure-based conceptual framework for systematic identification, classification, and aggregation of human pressures within ecosystem accounting. We developed a typology of pressures aligned with the SEEA-EA categories, using a functional interpretation: environmental variables are treated as pressures when they directly influence ecosystem exposure, fragmentation, or sensitivity.

This approach ensures coherent representation of relevant pressures for ecosystem condition, even if they do not strictly fit stock-flow distinctions, and aligns with European environmental policy and accounting practices. Recent work on the SEEA-CF revision (Obst and Bogaart, 2025) emphasizes the need for more spatially explicit

accounting of pressures, particularly residual flows, by linking them to impacted ecosystem types. While these developments focus on accounting-based pressures, they highlight the novelty of our framework, which provides an explicit, operational method for representing pressures.

Importantly, under SEEA-EA, land conversion is already captured within ecosystem extent accounts. Treating area loss as a pressure would therefore risk double counting. HPI avoids this by representing land-use pressure through fragmentation and management intensity rather than surface loss, ensuring compatibility with extent and condition accounts, while capturing structural and diffuse pressures beyond land conversion alone. Additionally, operationalising condition indicators can blur the line between pressures and condition variables, with the former sometimes used as proxies (Vallecillo et al., 2022), risking circularity. Our pressure typology resolves this by explicitly assigning each variable to a single category (e.g., imperviousness as a pressure, green spaces area as condition), ensuring conceptual clarity and avoiding circularity. Overall, the proposed framework, implemented through HPI, operationalises the SEEA principles transparently and in a policy-relevant manner, delivering cumulative, spatially explicit assessments of human pressures. It complements existing ecosystem extent, condition, and service accounts. Similarly, by explicitly distinguishing pressure and ecosystem state indicators, HPI enhances the consistency of the DPSIR framework.

4.3.2. Integration of IPBES drivers of biodiversity loss

By quantifying three major direct drivers of biodiversity loss, i.e., land-use, pollution and IAS (IPBES, 2019), HPI provides an explicit,

Fig. 5. Spatial distribution of invasive alien species pressure across Europe. IAS pressure is derived from reported occurrence records and reflects spatial patterns of invasion pressure rather than confirmed absence. Insets show (A) low IAS pressure in Northern and mountainous regions, (B) high pressure in highly connected regions of Western and Central Europe, and (C) intermediate pressure levels in parts of Southern Europe.

spatially structured representation of key anthropogenic drivers. These drivers are integrated within a pressure-based framework structured around IPBES driver categories, enabling the assessment of cumulative and potentially synergistic pressures that jointly alter ecosystem structure, processes and functions. Unlike global indices such as the Human Footprint Index (Venter et al., 2016) or the Global Human Modification Index (Theobald et al., 2025), which focus primarily on land-use change and infrastructure density, HPI's multi-driver approach provides a more holistic representation of human impacts. This enhances its relevance for ecosystem-based management and supports international biodiversity frameworks.

4.3.3. Spatial resolution and alignment with European policy and planning

HPI's 1-km² resolution balances European-scale coverage with landscape-level detail, aligning with ecological and administrative units such as Natura 2000 sites and biogeographic regions. This resolution makes it effective for identifying pressure hotspots and informing conservation planning and green-infrastructure investment. While the index is not intended for site-level management decisions, it provides a harmonised spatial baseline suitable for strategic environmental planning and monitoring across regional, national and European policy levels. HPI offers a harmonised baseline for spatial planning and environmental regulation, supporting tools like Environmental Impact Assessments (EIAs) and Strategic Environmental Assessments (SEAs). Its modular design, allowing independent use Pollution, Land-use and IAS components, enhances flexibility across diverse policy and management contexts.

As a monitoring tool, HPI enables tracking cumulative pressures over time, and supports evaluation of major EU initiatives, including the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) greening measures, the Zero Pollution Action Plan, the Soil Strategy for 2030, and the Nature Restoration Regulation. It can help detect tipping points and knowledge gaps, supporting adaptive management and forward-looking planning. HPI aligns with emerging requirements for spatially consistent assessments of ecosystem pressures and conditions, reinforced by the EU Soil Monitoring Legislation (EU, 2025), which emphasizes harmonised, spatially explicit evaluations for environmental planning and policy assessment.

Finally, HPI strengthens the scientific basis of European accounting initiatives, such as MAES and the INCA programme (Integrated Natural Capital Accounting), facilitating harmonised reporting under the SEEA-EA framework. By linking SEEA-EA accounting principles, IPBES driver typologies and EU policy targets, HPI demonstrates how spatially explicit, multi-driver indicators can support research, monitoring and action for biodiversity conservation and ecosystem restoration across Europe.

4.3.4. Stakeholder engagement and participatory relevance

Beyond its technical applications, HPI can contribute to stakeholder engagement and public awareness. By translating complex environmental data into accessible and visually intuitive outputs, it can enhance public understanding and facilitate participatory decision-making among citizens, practitioners, and policymakers. This transparency can foster shared responsibility for ecosystem stewardship and encourage sustainable land-use practices.

Fig. 6. Relationship between the BII and the HPI. A Beta-family GAM reveals nonlinear decline in BII with increasing HPI (blue line). The red dashed lines mark the HPI_{50} at which BII declines to half its baseline. The green dashed lines indicate the inflection point HPI_{sat} , where biodiversity loss transitions from rapid decline to a slower, saturating response. The black dotted line shows the lower asymptote of BII under extreme human pressure. Hexagons show the density of 1-km² pixels (log-scaled counts). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

4.4. Limitations of the Human Pressure Index

4.4.1. Spatial resolution and data granularity

Although HPI outputs are produced on a 1-km² grid, several underlying pressure indicators rely on datasets with coarser native resolutions. This mismatch may smooth spatial patterns and introduce uncertainty. While this resolution is suitable for continental-scale assessments and policy harmonisation, it is not adequate for fine-scale ecological processes or local management needs, such as urban planning or riparian restoration. Developing harmonised, wall-to-wall environmental datasets with a common high resolution, consistent with the interoperability principles of the INSPIRE directive (EU (European Union), 2007), will be essential for strengthening cumulative-pressure indices like HPI, improving spatially explicit ecosystem-condition accounts under SEEA-EA and enhancing applicability for local management.

4.4.2. Data limitations and spatio-temporal decoupling of pressures

HPI is constrained by incomplete and uneven environmental data coverage. Key pressures indicators, as pathogens and diseases, and species exploitation, are currently missing, despite their dominance in certain ecosystems. Temporal mismatches among datasets further increase uncertainty, particularly in rapidly changing landscapes. Improved coordination of monitoring systems and spatial reporting across Europe would facilitate the future integration of missing pressures and reduce temporal inconsistencies, enabling progressive refinement of indicators within the modular structure of HPI. Access to high-resolution data on pesticide applications, fertiliser surpluses and heavy-metal inputs remains constrained across Europe by confidentiality and data-protection regulations, which typically require aggregation at coarse administrative levels (Lampach et al., 2025). Reporting biases also affect indicators, especially IAS, where uneven monitoring effort across countries can create spatial artefacts or underestimate risks. Differences in national reporting standards reduce spatial comparability, underscoring the need for greater harmonisation of European environmental datasets. Additionally, several pressures exhibit spatial

or temporal decoupling from their ecological impacts. For example, pesticide loads, estimated from sales data, may underestimate actual exposure, due to atmospheric transport and deposition beyond agricultural areas (López et al., 2025). Ecological responses may also lag behind pressures due to accumulation, sublethal effects or altered species interactions (Rondeau et al., 2014). Similar decoupling occurs for pressures mediated by atmospheric, hydrological or landscape connectivity (Krauss et al., 2010).

4.4.3. Simplifying assumptions in the additive impact framework

The additive cumulative-impact framework, widely applied in terrestrial (Sutherland et al., 2022) and marine (Korpinen et al., 2021) contexts, assumes linear and independent contributions of stressors. In reality, pressures may interact in additive, synergistic or antagonistic ways, depending on biotic interactions (Orr et al., 2020) and on interactions among stressors themselves (Côté et al., 2016). This may underestimate nonlinearities, thresholds and amplified cumulative impacts (Schäfer and Piggott, 2018). Despite these limitations, the additive approach ensures transparency and reproducibility and remains appropriate for a first pan-European pressure index. Explicitly accounting for interactions among pressures represents an important direction for future developments of HPI, incorporating nonlinear modelling frameworks or interaction-based cumulative impact approaches while preserving compatibility with ecosystem-accounting applications.

4.4.4. Uncertainty in indicator weighting and missing drivers

The current weighting scheme, while based on the IPBES assessment and expert input, remains vulnerable to bias. Expanding the weighting process to include participatory approaches, involving policymakers, practitioners and civil society, could improve both legitimacy and contextual relevance.

Species exploitation was not included due to the lack of harmonised, spatially explicit datasets. Although partial information exists (e.g. national forest inventories), it remains too coarse for integration into a continental index. Climate change, despite its growing importance and

interactions with other pressures (e.g., drought amplifying pollution impacts), was also omitted. Future developments of HPI could integrate improved spatial proxies for species exploitation and high-resolution climate-risk layers to better capture compounded pressures, aligning with IPBES's focus on climate–biodiversity synergies.

5. Conclusion

The Human Pressure Index operationalizes a scalable conceptual framework, aligned with the SEEA-EA and IPBES principles, for mapping cumulative anthropogenic pressures across ecosystems. While demonstrated here for Europe, the underlying typology enables adaptation to other regions through the selection and integration of context-specific pressure indicators, provided that sufficiently harmonised spatial datasets are available. This ensures conceptual consistency with global biodiversity monitoring standards. By integrating land-use, pollution, and IAS pressures, HPI provides policymakers with a transparent and policy-relevant tool to support conservation and restoration priority setting, environmental planning, and the design, implementation, and evaluation of environmental policies across governance levels. Although challenges such as data granularity and the integration of additional IPBES drivers remain, the HPI's modular design and standardized methodology position it as a reference framework for evidence-based conservation and sustainable land-use planning across regional, national and continental scales.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Xavier Lecomte: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Valentine Aubard:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Graciela M. Rusch:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Bálint Czúcz:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Eszter Tanács:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Isabel Nicholson Thomas:** Writing – review & editing. **Chiara Cortinovis:** Writing – review & editing. **Sara Vallecillo:** Writing – review & editing. **Joana Seguin:** Writing – review & editing. **Fernando Santos-Martín:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Adrienne Grêt-Regamey:** Writing – review & editing. **Philip Roche:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used Le Chat (Mistral AI) and OpenAI ChatGPT to improve English language and readability, and to assist in coding. After using these tools, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content and code as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2026.114796>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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